

A Mixed Reality Eye-Tracking Study on Visual Influences in Dietary Choices

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Abstract

This study explores a new method for studying food consumption behaviors using eye-tracking in a Mixed Reality (MR) environment. Participants wear video see-through headsets and interact with various food scenarios while their gaze patterns are tracked. The study combines these metrics with questionnaires and immersive visuals to analyze eating habits. Expected results aim to show that carnivorous participants focus more on meat, vegetarians engage more with sustainable food choices, and omnivores respond to a broader range of factors. The findings are expected to highlight the potential of MR eye-tracking to reveal hidden preferences and inform tailored educational and marketing strategies based on dietary habits.

Introduction

Traditional methods such as questionnaires and food diaries, while frequently utilized, often face issues with biases and are inadequate in capturing the complex motivations behind food choices [1], [2]. Recent advances in Extended Reality (XR) technologies, including Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), and Mixed Reality (MR), have revolutionized the study of food choices by enabling controlled experiments in immersive and realistic virtual settings [3]. These technologies, particularly when combined with eye-tracking metrics, offer more objective insights into cognitive and emotional responses to food stimuli [4]. However, comprehensive research employing MR to explore sustainable practices remains limited. This study aims to fill these gaps by integrating traditional questionnaires with MR eye-tracking, offering a more objective and immersive evaluation of food preferences and sustainable choices. The adaptable nature of MR allows for rapid shifts between scenarios, delivering deeper, more detailed insights into dietary behaviors, and promotes a better understanding of demographic trends and sustainable food practices.

Methodology

This study employs eye-tracking in Mixed Reality (MR) to evaluate participant engagement by analyzing essential metrics such as gaze direction, duration, and fixation frequency. By refining gaze duration thresholds, the investigation differentiates between quick glances and more meaningful visual engagement. Participants interact with virtual food items in an MR environment, using XR hardware and the OpenXR framework. Their gaze behaviors are tracked, and data on gaze points, duration, and fixation locations are visualized through heatmaps. Additionally, quaternion rotation data of gaze direction is converted into Euler coordinates, allowing for a more precise analysis of gaze direction.

Experimental Setup

The flowchart in Fig. 1 outlines the study's approach to exploring the link between visual attention and food decision-making. Participants' preferences are evaluated in an MR setting, where a variety of food options are presented on a table with immersive 3D visuals. This setup is specifically designed for eye-tracking research, capturing detailed interactions with different food items. Eye-tracking data is gathered using Unity and the Oculus OVR Eye Gaze component, tracking participants' gaze as they interact with virtual food items. The system records gaze fixations and processes metrics like direction, duration, and fixation points. These metrics are then analyzed alongside questionnaire data to better understand food choices. Results are visualized using 3D heatmaps that highlight areas of high visual interest and identify food items that capture attention. By combining quantitative eye-tracking data with qualitative feedback, the study provides a thorough understanding of food habits and preferences.

Figure 1. Extended Reality-Based Behavioral Analysis Flowchart: Identifying Dietary Choices through Eye-Tracking, Heatmaps and Data Analysis.

Assessment of Participants

The study surveyed 114 participants, uncovering a range of food preferences and significant differences across gender, BMI, and health concerns between carnivores, vegetarians, and vegans. The carnivorous group had a higher proportion of males and elevated obesity rates, reflecting gender and cultural impacts as well as the potential advantages of plant-based diets.

Table 1. shows a higher proportion of males in the carnivorous group compared to the vegetarian and vegan groups, suggesting gender and cultural influences on dietary choices.

Table 1: Comparison of Dietary Groups Across Various Categories

Category	Vegetarians (incl. Vegans)	Omnivorous	Carnivorous
Age groups			
18-24	28.57%	6.19%	0%
25-34	14.29%	23.71%	14.29%
35-44	28.57%	56.70%	57.14%
45-54	0%	7.22%	0%
55-64	0%	3.09%	14.29%
65+	28.57%	3.09%	14.29%
Gender Distribution			
Male	28.57%	37.11%	71.43%
Female	71.43%	60.82%	28.57%
Non-binary	0%	2.06%	0%
Prefer not to say	0%	2.08%	0%
BMI (Body Mass Index)			
Underweight	0%	2.06%	0%
Normal Weight	57.14%	63.92%	28.57%
Overweight	42.86%	47.42%	42.86%
Obese	0%	6.18%	0%
Environmental Impact Concerns			
Very Low	0%	13.40%	14.29%
Low	0%	17.53%	28.57%
Moderate	42.86%	47.42%	42.86%
High	42.86%	19.59%	14.29%
Very High	14.29%	2.06%	0%
Health Concerns			
Very Low	0%	4.12%	0%
Low	0%	7.22%	42.86%
Moderate	42.86%	47.42%	42.86%
High	28.57%	42.27%	14.29%
Very High	14.29%	8.25%	0%
Ethical Concerns			
Yes	71.43%	27.08%	0%
No	28.57%	72.92%	100%

In addition, as illustrated in Fig. 2, taste was the most important factor influencing food choices, followed by health, cost, convenience, and freshness.

Figure 2. a) Key Factors affecting food habits, and b) BMI of participants

Mixed Reality Demonstration

Immersive Mixed Reality (MR) content was created to examine the relationship between participants' eye movements and the factors influencing their food choices, incorporating data storytelling to boost engagement (as shown in Fig. 3). Nutritional values for the food scenarios were calculated using the NRF9.3 method [5], while estimates for CO2 emissions, water, and land use were sourced from existing research [6]. Participant interactions, including eye tracking, clicks, and gaze duration, were carefully monitored within the MR environment.

Figure 3. Mixed Reality Environment Setting with Data Storytelling Visuals

Table 2. presents the engagement metrics, such as clicks and gaze duration, for carnivorous, vegetarian, and omnivorous participants across different food scenarios. Omnivorous participants showed higher levels of engagement, likely due to the variety and complexity of their diet, while carnivorous participants focused more on meat-based scenarios. This highlights the MR environment's effectiveness in engaging participants with content that matches their specific dietary preferences.

Table 2. Results of Number of Gazes, Total, Max, and Average Gaze Duration per Food Scenario at a sampling ratio of $f = 50$ Hz and minimum gaze fixation > 0.15 s

Group	Scenario	Count Total	Gaze (s)	Avg (s)	Max(s)
Vegetarian	Carbonara	2	0.42	0.21	0.26
	Lentil Soup	24	9.26	0.39	1.36
	Butter	10	3.72	0.37	0.88
	Beef Stake	13	8.06	0.62	1.44
	Bean Soup	5	1.62	0.32	0.52
	Buratta Salad	31	17.06	0.55	3.48
Omnivorous	Carbonara	39	26.54	0.68	4.22
	Lentil Soup	17	21.10	1.24	5.28
	Butter	14	8.76	0.63	2.14
	Beef Stake	21	12.68	0.60	1.78
	Bean Soup	17	8.76	0.52	2.24
	Buratta Salad	22	17.94	0.82	3.46
Carnivorous	Carbonara	29	14.16	0.48	1.80
	Lentil Soup	21	11.24	0.54	2.42
	Butter	24	7.60	0.32	1.02
	Beef Stake	41	19.28	0.47	1.76
	Bean Soup	25	12.24	0.49	1.20
	Buratta Salad	38	17.66	0.46	1.76

Heatmaps produced within the MR environment (Fig. 4) for an omnivorous participant highlighted areas of intense visual focus, providing insights into how individuals visually engage with specific food scenarios.

Figure 4. Visual attention heatmaps generated within the MR environment for omnivorous participant

Furthermore, the eye-tracking analysis showed that carnivorous participants tended to engage more with less healthy and sustainable food options but also demonstrated significant interest in health, GHG, and water usage metrics as shown in Table 3. This suggests potential opportunities to educate these groups about the environmental consequences of their dietary choices.

Table 3. Number of User clicks, Number of Gazes, Total, Average and Max Gaze duration on several key metrics for all food scenarios

Group	Factor	Clicks	Count Total	Gaze (s)	Avg (s)	Max(s)
Carnivorous	Health	20	30	9.70	0.32	0.68
	Water Use	19	69	26.24	0.38	1.58
	Price	19	65	28.58	0.44	1.16
	Land	12	60	20.78	0.34	1.28
	GHG	20	25	9.46	0.38	1.34
	Convenience	12	47	20.44	0.44	4.58
Vegetarian	Health	9	7	1.64	0.23	0.36
	Water Use	4	14	3.60	0.26	0.52
	Price	4	7	2.24	0.32	0.80
	Land	3	18	4.46	0.25	0.38
	GHG	5	17	3.88	0.23	0.36
	Convenience	5	25	8.28	0.33	1.00
Omnivorous	Health	11	69	41.08	0.59	2.88
	Water Use	10	66	35.60	0.54	3.64
	Price	13	69	38.72	0.56	3.46

	Land	10	59	33.86	0.57	2.80
	GHG	10	64	34.16	0.53	3.58
	Convenience	12	29	10.08	0.35	0.68

Conclusions and Future Studies

As expected, the MR environment assessment showed that participants with sustainable dietary habits spent more time interacting with sustainable food options, while those with carnivorous diets focused more on meat-based scenarios. The true potential of this tool lies in its ability to uncover deeper behavioral patterns. Future research will refine the tool by integrating additional metrics, such as selection behaviors and physiological responses (e.g., pupil dilation and heart rate), to further enhance its capability. The results will be expanded by developing new MR scenarios covering a wider array of consumer behaviors, including themes like circular economy and climate resilience. This approach will collect valuable data on how specific campaigns can successfully promote sustainable practices, ultimately contributing to societal acceptance and the success of sustainability-promoting policies.

References

1. Sember, V., Meh, K., Sorić, M., Starc, G., Rocha, P., and Jurak, G. (2020). Validity and Reliability of International Physical Activity Questionnaires for Adults across EU Countries: Systematic Review and Meta Analysis. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17. <https://doi.org/10.3390/>
2. Svendsen M, Tonstad S. Accuracy of food intake reporting in obese subjects with metabolic risk factors. *Br J Nutr*. 2006 Mar;95(3):640-9. doi: 10.1079/bjn20051662. PMID: 16512951
3. Manzoni, G. M., Cesa, G. L., Bacchetta, M., Castelnuovo, G., Conti, S., Gaggioli, A., and Riva, G. (2016). Virtual Reality-Enhanced Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy for Morbid Obesity: A Randomized Controlled Study with 1 Year FollowUp. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 19(2), 134-140. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cyber.2015.0208>
4. Ruppenthal, T. (2023). Eye-Tracking Studies on Sustainable Food Consumption: A Systematic Literature Review. *Sustainability*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su152316434>
5. Sluik D, Streppel MT, van Lee L, Geelen A, Feskens EJ. Evaluation of a nutrient-rich food index score in the Netherlands. *J Nutr Sci*. 2015 Apr 20;4:e14. doi:10.1017/jns.2015.4. PMID: 26097700; PMCID: PMC4462757.
6. Poore J., Nemecek T., Reducing food's environmental impacts through producers and consumers, *Science*, Vol 360, Issue:6392, pp. 987-992, DOI:10.1126/science.aag0216